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RESEARCH ON THE HYDROBIOCHEMICAL STATE OF LAKE LISI WATER

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რეზიუმე

ტბების ძლიერმა დაბინძურებამ ანთროპოგენური და ბუნებრივი ფაქტორების მეშვეობით, შეიძლება გამოიწვიოს ევტროფიკაციის პროცესი - წყლის ბინადრებში ბიოგენური ელემენტების დაგროვება. ევტროფიკაცია კვლავ რჩება წყლის ხარისხის მართვის მთავარ პრობლემად შიდა წყლებისთვის: როგორც ტბებისთვის, ასევე წყალსაცავებისთვის. საქართველო წყლის რესურსებით მდიდარი ქვეყანაა, მათ შორის 856 ტბაა. არსებული ტბებიდან ერთერთია ქალაქ თბილისის ქვაბულში მდებარე ლისის ტბა, რომელიც ჩვენი კვლევის საგანია. ის წარმოადგენს მოსახლეობისათვის საუკეთესო დასასვენებელ, რეკრეაციულ ზონას. ჩატარებული იქნა ლისის ტბის მონიტორინგი. შესწავლილი იყო მისი ფიზიკურ-გეოგრაფიული, კლიმატური მდგომარეობა. ფიზიკურ-ქიმიური კვლევების შედეგად გამოვლენილი იქნა, რომ წყალი ხასიათდება მაღალი მარილიანობით, ორგანული დაბინძურებით, ჟანგბადდეფიციტით და ევტროფიკაციის ნიშნებით, ხოლო მიკრობიოლოგიური ანალიზმა გვიჩვენა, რომ ყველა სანიტარულ მაჩვენებელში ფიქსირდება გადაჭარბება და წყალი ეპიდემიოლოგიურად საფრთხის შემცველია. დადგინდა, ლისის ტბის წყალი არ აკმაყოფილებს რეკრეაციულ მოთხოვნებს და საჭიროებს შესაბამის გარემოსდაცვით და სარეაბილიტაციო ღონისძიებებს.

Abstract

Severe pollution of lakes through anthropogenic and natural factors can lead to the process of eutrophication - the accumulation of biogenic elements in aquatic organisms. Eutrophication remains the main problem of water quality management for inland waters: both lakes and reservoirs. Georgia is a country rich in water resources, including 856 lakes. One of the existing lakes is Lake Lisi, located in the Tbilisi Basin, which is the subject of our study. It is the best resting and recreational zone for the population. Its physical-geographical and climatic conditions were studied. As a result of physical-chemical studies, it was revealed that the water is characterized by high salinity, organic pollution, oxygen deficiency and signs of eutrophication, while microbiological analysis showed that all sanitary indicators are exceeded and the water is epidemiologically dangerous. It was determined that the water of Lake Lisi does not meet recreational requirements and requires appropriate environmental protection and rehabilitation measures.

საკვანძო სიტყვები: ლისის ტბა, რეკრეაციული ზონა, მონიტორინგი, კვლევა, ანალიზი, დაბინძურება.

Keywords: Lisi Lake, recreational zone, monitoring, research, analysis, Pollution.

Introduction

Georgia is rich in water resources, including 856 lakes. Pollution of water bodies can occur from various sources. In recent years, water consumption has increased sharply in both urban and rural areas. Accordingly, water pollution has increased and has become widespread, which is due to the mixing of

polluted water into rivers and lakes, which damages the ecosystem and threatens the existence of small lakes. [1,2].

Lakes, both natural and man-made, are subject to urban, industrial, agricultural, and other impacts. Severe pollution of lakes through anthropogenic and natural factors can lead to the process of eutrophication

- the accumulation of biogenic elements in aquatic organisms [3].

Eutrophication remains a major water quality management problem for inland waters: both lakes and reservoirs. The way to stop the degradation is to stop the sources of nutrients and accelerate the recovery in lakes with the help of technologies. Eutrophication in the initial stages leads to an increase in the biological productivity of water bodies, and then to a progressive lack of oxygen and, consequently, to the massive death of living organisms. Many measures have been developed regarding eutrophication, including the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) [6, 9].

Approaches to preventing and reversing eutrophication include minimizing pollution from point sources such as sewage and agriculture, as well as other non-point sources of pollution. In addition, the introduction of bacteria and algae inhibitory organisms, which also help reduce nitrogen pollution, in turn controls the growth of cyanobacteria, which is the main source of algal blooms.

A global practice on watershed restoration has been developed – the UN Decade of Ecosystem Restoration. Key themes include holistic approaches, lake-specific diagnostics, and integrated management to address pollution, sedimentation, and changing demands, with efforts increasingly integrating climate adaptation and circular economy principles [10, 11].

Characterization of the research object

The object of the study is Lake Lisi, monitoring its pollution. Lake Lisi is located in the Tbilisi Basin, northwest of the city. Lisi - height above sea level - 624 m., lake area - 0.47 km², basin area - 16.1 km², maximum depth -4.0 km², average depth -2.60 m, lake volume - 1.22 million. M³. The Lisi Lake basin is separated from the surrounding areas by low and medium-height hilly terrain. The lake is of a closed type and currently, the surface area of the lake varies from 40-50 ha. The development of the lake area began a long time ago. Currently, Lake Lisi is one of the most popular recreation and areas health in the city. In 2007, the new Tbilisi Hippodrome was opened near it, covering an area of 31 hectares and is a favorite place for horse riding enthusiasts. In recent years, the shoreline of Lake Lisi has been rehabilitated: a recreation area has been renovated, a beach has been

arranged, and a coastal path has been laid. A new thermal bath has been opened (there are several thermal springs around the lake). Fish are bred in the lake. After the improvement of Lake Lisi, the flow of citizens, water sports enthusiasts, and fishing enthusiasts has significantly increased, and accordingly, anthropogenic pollution is expected to increase [8]. Based on the above, it is important to monitor the pollution of Lake Lisi.

Methods and analysis results

For the complex research conducted on Lake Lisi (hydrochemical, physicochemical, and microbiological), a modern, field-based mobile device, the latest laboratory equipment, and internationally recognized methods were used. Due to the goals and objectives of the study, only licensed ISO standards were used. According to its nutrition, it is a mixed-type water body, fed by rain, snowmelt, and groundwater [4.5.7].

The water level maintains high levels in spring, and low levels in autumn. In summer, the water is warm, with a maximum temperature of 28 °C. In winter, an ice edge and sometimes an ice cover appear on the lake. The water is brackish (mineralization 2060 mg/l).

The organoleptic characteristics of water were determined, one of the important indicators of which is temperature, which to some extent shows the speed and direction of water quality changes. Affects the physical, chemical and biological processes taking place in the reservoir, which actually determine the oxygen regime of water and the intensity of the self-purification process [12].

An informative indicator of water quality is the pH value. It determines the natural properties of water and, at the same time, is an indicator of its pollution. In clean waters, the pH value varies within the range of 6.5 - 8.5. The water of Lake Lisi is characterized by weak alkalinity. The pH value varies within the range of pH = 8.00 - 8.27 . Therefore, the content of heavy metals in dissolved form is not expected in the water, which is also evident from the research results. From the sanitary characteristics of water quality, we identified: biological oxygen demand (BOD), dissolved oxygen and biogenic compounds: ammonium salts, nitrites, nitrates and phosphates. The analysis results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Organoleptic and physicochemical indicators of Lake Lisi

#	Name	Unit	Measurement results	MPC	Method used
1	Temperature °C	°C	12		
2	Smell	Bali	Odorless	2	ISO 6658
3	Turbidity	NTU	5,2	3,5	ISO 7027
4	Electrical conductivity	µS/cm	$30,4 \cdot 10^{-2}$		ISO 7888:1985
5	Mineralization	ppm or mg/l	2060	300-1200	Total Dissolved Solids - TDS
6	pH		7,8		ISO 10523.94
7	Dissolved oxygen (O ₂)	mg/l	6,4	4 -6	ASTM D888
8	Ammonium (NH ₄ ⁺)	mg/l	0,51	0,39	ISO 7150-1:2010
9	Nitrite (NO ₂ ⁻)	mg/l	0.014	1,0	ISO 10304-1:2007
10	Nitrate (NO ₃ ⁻)	mg/l	0.045	10	
11	Phosphate (PO ₄ ³⁻)	mg/l	0.145	3,5	
12	Sulfates (SO ₄ ²⁻)	mg/l	2035.16	500	
13	Chlorides (Cl ⁻)	mg/l	168.89	350	
14	Calcium (Ca ⁺²)	mg/l	148	140	
15	Hardness	mg.eq/l	12	10	

As can be seen from the table, only the values of dissolved oxygen, ammonium ion, calcium, hardness and sulfates slightly exceed the maximum permissible concentration. The high content of ammonium ion indicates that the intensity of the processes that cause its accumulation prevails here, i.e. degradation of protein compounds, deamination of amino acids, etc.

Accordingly, mineralization and electrical conductivity are also high..

For the assessment of water quality, great importance is attached to the assessment of sanitary conditions, for which a microbiological study of the water of Lake Lisi was conducted, the results of which are given in Table 2.

Table 2.

Microbiological analysis indicators of Lake Lisi water

Research parameters	Significance of indicators in relation to ND	Actual value of indicators	Research methods
The value of mesophilic aerobes and facultative anaerobes in 1 ml	$37^{\circ}\text{C} \leq 20$ $22^{\circ}\text{C} \leq 100$	96 240	SST ISO 6222-2008
Total coliform bacteria, per 300 ml	Not allowed	960	SST ISO 9308 - 1:2014/2014
E.coli, in 300 ml	Not allowed	22	SST ISO 9308 - 1:2014/2014
Faecal streptococci (Faecalis), in 250 ml	Not allowed	59	SST ISO 7899 - 2/2007

The results of microbiological analysis show minor water pollution. E.coli, common coliforms, and fecal streptococcus bacteria were detected in the water.

Conclusion

The results of the study showed that the water of Lake Lisi is subject to strong anthropogenic impact, fecal pollution, high mineralization and salinity, oxygen deficiency and signs of eutrophication. This condition indicates ecosystem degradation, does not meet recreational requirements and requires appropriate environmental protection and rehabilitation measures. Therefore, biological cleaning measures will be implemented and repeated studies are planned.

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